

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics

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Supplementary material: VALIDATION OF THE VOCABULARY OF OntoFoCE

A work that can be considered as a reference of the corpus is that of [Banday, 2011], where he describes the architecture of an email, clearly defining each identifiable component or part of the email, as well as the technical processes necessary to describe how the transmission occurs. OntoFoCE includes concepts beyond forensic analysis. These have been incorporated in the ontology to establish an email's traceability from the transmission process's representation.

Table 1 is based on the work previously mentioned. It describes the different elements or concepts of an electronic email, which can be integrated into a *corpus* related to emails. This table also shows which elements or concepts are represented in OntoFoCE.

The first column of the table identifies the term. The second and third columns show the name of the term as proposed by [Banday, 2011] and the definition of the type of element, respectively. Then the fourth column presents the description of the term to clarify details that the name of the term itself does not express. Finally, the last column shows OntoFoCE's concept or attribute associated with that term. Each row in the table represents a term according to the email architecture proposal [Banday, 2011]

Table 1: Corpus of email-related terms

N°	Term	Type	Brief Description	OntoFoCE concept or attribute associated with the element
1	Autor	Mail component	Responsible for creating the message, its content, and its list of recipients	aliasUser
2	Receptor	Mail component	Consumer of the delivered message	RecipientAccount
3	Return Controller	Transmission process	Process that reports shipment failures.	
4	Mediator	Transmission process	A process that receives, adds, reformulates, and redistributes messages between authors and recipients.	
5	Originator	Transmission process	Process that ensures the validity of the message and then sends it. Handles any problems about mail transmission.	
6	Relay	Transmission process	Process responsible for routing the shipment and is responsible for adding tracking information in the mail header.	
7	Gateway	Transmission process	Process that connects heterogeneous mail services despite differences in syntax and semantics.	
8	Receptor	Transmission process	Process that makes the final delivery or sends the message to an alternative address in case of failure in the shipment.	
9	Edge	Transmission process	Process responsible for transferring networks to the edge of the open Internet.	
10	Consumidor	Transmission process	Edge service, common for web-based email access	EmailClient
11	Transit	Transmission process	Email Service Providers	internetServiceProvider
12	SMTP	Protocol and script	Communication protocol for the transfer of mail between the sending computer and the server of the issuing account.	
13	SMTP*	Protocol and script	RFC-compliant SMTP protocol suite	
14	HTTP	Protocol and script	Hypertext Transfer Protocol, acting over SSL and TLS	

N°	Term	Type	Brief Description	OntoFoCE concept or attribute associated with the element
15	INT	Protocol and script	Specific protocols and procedures for internal email delivery between nodes in the same domain	
16	IMAP	Protocol and script	Communication protocol for mail transfer from the receiving account's server.	
17	POP3	Protocol and script	Protocol to download mail from the receiving account's server	
18	Message-ID	Mail component	Unique message identification string generated when sent.	idEmail
19	In-Reply-To	Mail component	Contains the ID of the original message that the reply message is sent.	idEmail
20	References	Mail component	Identifies other documents related to this message, such as another email message.	
21	From	Mail component	Name and email address of the author of the message.	SenderAccount aliasUser
22	Sender	Mail component	Address responsible for sending the message on behalf of the author, if not omitted or the same as specified in the From field	ReceptionAccount
23	Reply-to	Mail component	Email address, which the author wants recipients to use for replies.	
24	Date	Transmission process	Date and time the message was available for delivery	dateTimeOccurrence
25	Subject	Mail component	Describes the topic or subject of the message.	contentEmailSubject
26	Comments	Mail component	Contains summary comments about the message.	
27	Keyword	Mail component	Contains a comma-separated list of keywords that may be useful to recipients, for example when searching for mail.	
28	TO	Mail component	Specifies a list of addresses of the recipients of the message.	ReceptionAccount
29	CC	Mail component	List of shipping addresses in addition to the main one	ReceptionAccount
30	BCC	Mail component	Hidden list of shipping addresses	ReceptionAccount
31	Resent Message-ID	Mail component	Unique message identification string generated when forwarded.	idEmail
32	Resent-*	Mail component	When manually forwarding a message, forward the header fields referring to the forwarding, not the original message.	ReceptionAccount
33	List-ID	Mail component	Identifying a mailing list	
34	List-*	Mail component	Set of emails that make up a distribution list	ReceptionAccount
35	Received	Mail component	Contains trace information including source host, mediator processes, relay and domain names and/or IP addresses	idDevice
36	Return-Path	Mail component	Contains the address registered in the From of the sent mail	SenderAccount
37	DKIM Signature	Protocol and script	The email signature is stored in the DKIM-Signature field of the header.	
38	Received-SPF	Protocol and script	Contains sender policy validation (SPF) results for a domain and its mail servers, about which machines are authorized to use your domain in the HELO and MAIL FROM fields.	
39	MIME Version	Mail component	Describes the version of the MIME message format.	

N°	Term	Type	Brief Description	OntoFoCE concept or attribute associated with the element
40	<i>Content-*</i>	<i>Mail component</i>	<i>Contains a collection of MIME fields that describe various aspects of the message body, including signatures.</i>	<i>contentEmailBody userSignature</i>
41	HELO/ EHLO	Protocol and script	Contains data about the hosting domain defined in the SMTP HELO and EHLO commands.	
42	ENVID	Protocol and script	A string included in the DSN Server to identify the recipient's return address.	
43	<i>MailFrom</i>	<i>Mail component</i>	<i>A string that contains the email address for postback control.</i>	<i>SenderAccount</i>
44	<i>RcptTo</i>	<i>Mail component</i>	<i>Specifies the mailbox address of a recipient.</i>	<i>ReceptionAccount</i>
45	ORCPT	Protocol and script	Optional parameter for the RCPT command, indicating the original direction to which the current RCPT TO is directed.	
46	<i>Source Address</i>	<i>Transmission process</i>	<i>Contains the source address of the previous host to the current receiving server from which the IP datagram was sent (the email message is fragmented into IP packets).</i>	<i>identificadorEquipo</i>

Considering the proposal of [Banday, 2011] described in Table 1, it is necessary to identify those corpus components included in OntoFoCE. Thus, depending on the function of each component, different types of elements have been defined:

- Components of the mail: those referring to the email itself (24 elements),
- Transmission Process: those that define the processes involved in the transmission process (11 elements), and
- Protocols and Script: the different protocols and command chains that govern the sending process (11 elements).

It is worth mentioning that only 18 elements included in the first section of these groups mentioned (written in bold and italics in the table) are relevant to the forensic analysis of emails; the rest are not considered because they do not contain data that contributes to the validity or existence of the email. These components that have been discarded are:

- *References*: This term usually contains information to identify other documents related to this message, such as another email message, but when forensic analysis requires correlation studies of several emails, it is always performed based on the email's sending/receiving data, not on its content.
- *Reply To*: This term refers to the email account the user wants the recipients to use for replies. This information is complementary for the forensic analysis of an email since the sending process is analyzed considering the sending and the recipient account.
- *Comments*: Here are summarized comments about the message, which –like the content of the body of the email– is not part of the forensic analysis to identify the validity or existence of the email.
- *Keyword*: The term contains a list of keywords, separated by commas, that can be useful to recipients, for example, when searching an email. It is not part of the forensic analysis for the same reasons as those indicated in the previous term.
- *List-ID*: This term identifies the distribution list, not the set of accounts that make up that distribution list. For that reason, it is not considered in forensic analysis.
- *MIME Version*: this element refers to the version of the MIME message format, it is not relevant to forensic analysis.

Only 4 of the 11 elements identified in the transmission process are used in forensic analysis (written in bold and italics in the table). The rest (*Return Controller, Mediator, Originator, Relay, Gateway, Receiver and Edge*) refer to processes that occur during the transmission of an email, but are not considered for forensic analysis because they do not modify the storage of an email in the transmission process; as a result, they do not have an impact on the occurrences. These data, as well as those related to encryption and antivirus protection that email clients generate, are ignored during forensic analysis.

REFERENCES

Banday, M. T. (2011). Techniques and Tools for Forensic Investigation of E- Mail. *International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA)*, 3(6), 227–241. <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijnsa.2011.3617>